

Socio-Cultural and Public Administration of Neolithic Mehrgrah, Baluchistan, Pakistan Civilization (7000-2500BC)

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Abstract— The work represents the Socio-Cultural and public Administration of Mehrgrah Civilization, Baluchistan, Pakistan (7000-2500BC). The people of Mehrgrah Civilization have mother and father based society, where the head of the family or tribe has the authority to decide for the well-being of the people after discussion with all members of the community. The head of the family or tribe may be designated with the name of Sardar stand for the person who led the family or tribe. They have a traditional system of punishment and rewards that they used for any individual after collective decision by the whole community. Generally, the head of family or tribe has used turban for his identity and honor which is still exist in the area. The majority of them were nomads and agrarians, however there have very little evidences regarding their political and governance system in the form of artifacts. The lifestyle and culture of Mehrgrah people has very simple and respectful from the earlier ages. They have enthusiastic agriculturists and worth their products. They have walls and ceilings of their houses for their protection and privacy. This effort of the people of Mehrgrah declared them the first well known industrial and agrarian society of the World history. Due to faster development in technology, the inhabitants of Mehrgrah civilization have started to use pottery, wheels, vases and vessels for their own use and trade with other communities of that era. They have also the ability to made defense tools like arrows, and swords from copper ores and also had long distance contact with the Mesopotamia, Central Asia and Greek civilization. They are also known for the rainwater logging system and its use for domestic and agriculture purposes like Sailaba and Trai system, the utmost thing started has of the technique of dental surgery and use of medicinal plants for different diseases. The archeologist believes that it has the foundation of medical sciences and these discoveries revealed that the inhabitants of the Civilization have intelligent to think about these and invented solution of their problems. One of the reason archeologists and most of the human believes that the people who lived in Mehrgrah were so civilized because they found the way clothes were stitched and they used to wear clothes because archeologist claims that use of cotton originated from Mehrgrah. This is why Pakistan cotton industry is considered one of the potential sectors for the economy of Pakistan.

Keywords— Social culture, Mehrgrah, Civilization, Pakistan.

I. INTRODUCTION

The work represents the Socio-Cultural and Public Administration of Neolithic Mehrgrah, Civilization Baluchistan, Pakistan (7000-2500BC)). The specific purpose of every section determines to produce and familiarize the main theme and key targets of the research. The term Public Administration derived from English word that is 'administer' which is originated from Latin term *ad* and *ministrare*, literally means to care for or to look after the inhabitants, to run associations. In its factual logic, the word 'administration' means supervision of public or private affairs. Generally, administration is a procedure allowing all communal efforts in public, private, military, government sectors and is thus of common nature [1]. However, administration is a humble meaning to care for or look after the community and to manage their relations. Several contributors have discussed the elements of public administration on international level. In which the utmost presented by [2] are; Planning, Organization, Command, Coordination and Control etc, (POCCC). He supposed that the administrative capability cannot be build up in the course of technological or scientific knowledge alone. Consequently, he has suggested an administrative training of employees at different stages. He has explained about six qualities of an administrative manager like physical, mental, moral, general education, special knowledge and experiences [3].

Politically, Pakistan divided into five provinces comprises of Sind, Punjab, Baluchistan, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa and Gilgit Baltistan province with two major federally administrative tribal areas and Azad Jammu and Kashmir. Historically, the territory of Pakistan comprises of three major ancient civilizations namely, Mehrgrah (Baluchistan, 7000-2500BC), Indus Valley Civilization (Punjab and Sind, 2500-1900BC) and Gandhara Civilization (Khyber Pakhtunkhwa and Afghanistan, 7000BC-1000AD). Mehrgrah is located at the Bolan Pass about 30 kilometers from Sibi, on the western direction of the Indus River. The civilization was well established on both sides of the Bolan River in Baluchistan (Pakistan). The Mehrgrah site was discovered by a French Archeologist, Jean-Francois Jarriger during 1974 and worked on it till 1986 (Figure-1). The premature facts have proposed that the Mehrgrah civilization has existed as early as 7000 BC, about 3500 years earlier than

the Indus Civilization. Mehrgrah is known by its unbelievable and well-planned ancient farm villages of ancient Pakistan [4].

Figure-1. Excavated Mehrgrah Village

Mehrgrah is an old civilization and historic settlement (7000-2500 BC) located on the Kechi plain of Baluchistan plateau (Pakistan) with sign of agricultural crops particularly wheat, barley, cotton and rearing of domestic animals like goats, cattle, and sheep. This civilization can be spread over the main western course along with Indus Valley as well as parts of Afghanistan. The archeology of this civilization has been distributed into several eras, the first one is Neolithic, pre-pottery era, which dates back to approximately 7000 B.C. or even from much earlier times. The civilization was uninhibited between 2000 to 2500 B.C. for the period of close contact with the Indus Valley civilization and later began to use again for funeral purpose for short time near 2000 B.C. Possibly, the dynamic aspect state of Mehrgrah is that one can easily observed its cyclic improvement from an premature rural community to a central region, which was spread over an area of 200 hectares. In the meantime, of progress, a well-developed site, which could be sign of authority and governance, was built at the area. Mehrgrah was also a focal point of manufacture for numerous collectibles and terracotta products, which were circulated to neighboring areas. Earlier researches show that people belonging here manage to be survived in houses and do hunting, reared animals and farm crops namely wheat and barley. The civilization of hunting and farming progressed steadily, and their occupations were artistic. The peoples of the civilization used tools made by bone and stonier particularly stone-axes, hard stone blades called (flint blades) and sharp bone pointers. Metal made and potter-wheel prepared devices were familiarized, and they created some well mud figures and pottery with glamorous geo-metric designs. Consequently, they fashioned a new style and use jewellery made of globules, gems that is lapis, lazuli and seashells [5].

The chronology of the Mehrgrah Civilization may be divided into many phases. The first phase ranges from 7000 to 3300 BCE (Early Food Producing Era). This stage is known by Mehrgrah first (Ceramic Neolithic) varies from 7000 to 5500 BCE, while the second phase of the era is known by the Mehrgrah phase-II and VI and designated by the name Ceramic Neolithic era (regionalization era) varies from 5500 to 3300 [6]. The second phase is called the Early Harapan or Indus Valley (Regional Era) varies from 3300 to 2600 BCE.

The main contributors who discussed the public administration of Mehrgrah Civilization in Baluchistan

Pakistan as well as international level comprises of; [7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14].

II. DATA & METHOD

The research methodology consists of objectives, hypothesis, questions, variables, data collection, sampling techniques, research tools, data analysis and research organization. The main objectives of the study are; to study the socio-Culture and public administration of Mehrgrah Civilization. The research objectives are followed by the research questions and hypothesis. The work based on the public administration as independent variable, whereas the political setup, government, population, facilities, economy, health, law, security, trade and business etc as dependent and intervening variables. Both of secondary as well as primary data have used to achieve the objectives of the study. The primary information regarding the local opinion have collected from the field using structure questionnaire, whereas, the secondary data about different previous workers as well as historical public administration etc. Accumulated from different secondary sources like internet, research papers, books, articles, and concerned departments at federal and provincial level. The site of Mehrgrah has visited for the observations and collection of artifacts from their archeological museum. The various tools used for the current research consists of personal discussions, stakeholders' interviews, field visits, focus group discussions, observations, literature review and schedule. The different procedures used during course of study are; to design a structure questionnaire and to share it with the locals as well as officials for the aim to understand their historical approaches randomly. To accomplish field visits, consultations and arguments with concerned executives and to understand their sights concerning the Socio-Culture and Public Administration in Mehrgrah Civilization and to collect evidences from different sites. A master sheet has devised from the collected information using computer technology and after data analysis all of the evidences have discussed and compiled.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Mehrgrah Civilization Period I (7000 BCE-5500 BCE)

The first phase of the civilization has recognized by the preliminary farming civilization having reared pottery industry. During this period the people has used plants, for instance wheat and barley, cattle, goats for farming as well as source of their nutrition. They have the ability to construct homes from mud for shelter and made baskets to carry food, stones and bangles and other tools for their basic needs. One of the reason archeologists and most of the human believes that the people who lived in Mehrgrah were so civilized because they found the way clothes were stitched and they used to wear clothes because archeologist claims that use of cotton originated from Mehrgrah. This is why Pakistan cotton industry is considered one of the potential sectors for the economy of Pakistan.

They have also the ability to bury the dead bodies of their family members with more honor and respect. They have also the experts of making Jewelry as well as seashells, which have worn by women. Furthermore, archeologists found the axe, which was made from stone and also toys of different birds and animals. The site of Mehrgrah spread over about 495 acres,

which was enough for the survival of the residence of the civilization, however, the archeologist still excavates and search for the secretes of their way of life at that time [4].

Nomads are the ancient one those settled in Mehrgrah. They had migrated from mountain areas to plain for pasturing in South. Then this migration brought many changes and many more ways found for nutrition like hunting and they learnt how to raise sheep and goats and other animals of that time. This was a time when things started to change and civilization started to develop in the people of that time and most of them became agriculturist and started farming and cultivation (Jarrige and Audouze, 1980). Due to innovations, the period has also known by the name Early Food-Processing Phase (ca. 7000–5500 BCE).

Authority and Governance

Mehrgrah, due to the broad flat unearthing, demonstrate an all-around delineated change from early agribusiness to the primers of urbanization [15]. In numerous early social orders, the family as a unit, or as a constituent piece of a group, grouped creatures and developed yields. More youthful individuals were relied upon to work for the senior citizens. This was work performed considering a family relationship connect and is before the acceptance of non-family work, which denotes a huge social flight however which presumably turns into an asset in the more created cultivating related with later, socially stratified societies. At the point when social orders turned out to be more perplexing and the framework changed, non-family work was included or supplanted kinfolk-based work.

This was the work of the individuals who were not family but rather were ready to work for reward, or, perhaps, on the off chance that they were prisoners they could be compelled to work for the individuals who had caught them. The utilization of non-kinfolk work additionally introduces the likelihood of an expansion in deliver and this would have brought up the issue of how the expansion was to be conveyed. Controlling and sorting out work in such circumstances, regardless of whether family based or not, would turn into a noteworthy wellspring of expert and one of the elements of the boss. This uncovers the general population of Mehrgrah were communist or socialist.

Settlements were not isolated and the interaction between them could have been through an exchange of goods associated with even a minimal specialization in the production of exchangeable items, such as beads, through pastoral circuits and migrations and through confrontations. These would have created networks to channel exchange on a more regular basis, together with marriage circles and new ritual practices. They have mother and father-based society,

Figure- 2. Communal Union

Where the head of the family or tribe has the authority to decide for the well-being of the people after discussion with all members of the community. The head of the family or tribe may be designated with the name of Sardar stand for the person who led the family or tribe. They have a traditional system of punishment and rewards that they used for any individual after collective decision by the whole community. Generally, the head of family or tribe has used turban for his identity and honor which is still exist in the area. They have dispersed settlements in the form of huts or villages having bricks made houses. The majority of them were nomads and agrarians, however there have very little evidences regarding their political and governance system in the form of artifacts (Figure-2).

Population of Mehrgrah Civilization

The planed town of Mehrgrah had a total population of 25000 inhabitants comprises of male and female. It has observed that the agriculture begins entirely from Near-East to South Asia having similarities in the agriculture as well as culture continuum with eastern Mesopotamia [16]. Generally, keeping in view the reality of the Mehrgrah, it has evident that this civilization has its own background," and has not a part of the Neolithic culture in the Near East.

[7] have stated that as there is a well-built connection among the Neolithic and Copper Age (Chalcolithic) civilization of Mehrgrah. The dental proof reveals that the copper age population has not the remains of Neolithic people of Mehrgrah and leads to the moderate stages of gene exchange. The evidence of the Neolithic people of Mehrgrah has observed throughout the south western part of the Indus Valley in Pakistan.

Lifestyle, Language and Culture

The lifestyle and culture of Mehrgrah people has very simple and respectful from the earlier ages. They have primarily constructed small houses having circular or rectangular in shape and made of mud and reed. Generally, living nearer to the Indus or Main River shows that if the river flooded, then the water would wash away their homes. Therefore, the inhabitants of the civilization have started to construct their homes by mud bricks. They have enthusiastic agriculturists and worth their products. They have women dominant society and always give respect to women have ability to fed and birth more children. Mostly, they have joint family system and nomadic culture. It is also found that they

have the ability to make thread from cotton and to use it for sewing of dresses. They have walls and ceilings of their houses for their protection and privacy. This effort of the people of Mehrgrah declared them the first well known industrial and agrarian society of the World history.

Among their utmost success of their lifestyle, it has fact that they have stored their agriculture products in drums made of mud to utilize it during off season. Eventually, they have progressed very faster and by 4000 BCE, they had started to live in two-story houses. Due to faster development in technology, the inhabitants of Mehrgrah civilization have started to use pottery, wheels, vases and vessels for their own use and trade with other communities of that era [17]. The general population of that time used to wear woolen or cotton garments. A portion of the gods had their plait on their back and bears. The greater part of the male statues wore turbans, which is still in vogue in Baluchistan. While the sentiment of a few archeologists that few of the statues found at the site may have been kids, there are numerous who interface these earthenware figures to the religious convictions of Mehrgrah individuals and the age-old idea of the intensity of nature and female gods [18].

Religion of Mehrgrah Civilization

Amid unearthing, the archeologists found earth female dolls related with ripeness ceremonies and accepted to have been loved by the locals. Comparable puppets have surface in other archeological locales in the region. A few of these statues are cut with the accessories and have their hands on their bosom or midsection. Some have kids on their laps. In addition, terracotta figures of bulls have additionally been found at Mehrgrah indicating the conceivable love of creatures or their lifted-up status as life-providers for the sustenance they yielded (Figure-3.2). In any case, our examination must be limited to the nearness of the goddess in the earthenware. Earthenware craftsmanship in the nation and for doing as such we will to peep into Mehrgrah, Mundigak, Kulli, Zhob destinations and the locales of Harappa, Mohen-Jo-Daro and others. Numerous archeological locales in Bihar have additionally yielded mother-goddess dolls. The dead were covered, both in flexed (with knees drawn up) and broadened positions. Grave contributions included consuming of youthful carpinies, the quantity of which changed with status of the dead [19].

Figure-3: Women Figurine and Mother goddess

Tools and Technology

During Neolithic Mehrgrah era, the locals have inventive craftsmen and develop different tools, ornaments and usable items from copper ore. They could process the

copper and use it for different purposes. A historical site dating back to 4500 years has discovered at Naesheroferoze district, Sind province having pottery industry. Generally,

about the 12 blades Splinters have found that made of copper and used for to trim and shape the different tools made of copper. They have also the ability to make baskets using

Figure-4: Tools and Technology of Mehrgrah, Whistles, War tools and Birds

woods, mud, and copper for their domestic use as well as commercial purposes.

The famous tools that found during excavation of comprises of borers and geometric micro-liths like lunates, triangles, trapezes, whistles, dolls, and other figurines. Besides, they have also the ability to made defense tools like arrows, and swords from copper ores and also had long distance contact with the Mesopotamia, Central Asia and Greek civilization (Figure-4). They are also known for the rainwater logging system and its use for domestic and agriculture purposes like Sailaba and Trai system [20].

Industry

Rather than copper made tools, the inhabitants of Mehrgrah have also the industry of making pottery and figurines from mud. It has their credit that they made fine, wheel-made pottery of 20–25cm diameter, with sharp borders, glide in red and black color. The Archaeologists classified the pottery into different types and name as ‘Togau Ware’ (Figure-5). The ‘Togau A’ has the initial era pottery of Mehrgrah having intricate designs of domestic animals internally and became

more simplistic with passage of time. Primarily, the inhabitants of Mehrgrah have produced the pottery items per their requirements but latter on they started to produce in a large number with the increase in population as well as their links with other Neolithic cultures of that time [20].

Figure-5: Industrial Products of Mehrgrah,

Mehrgrah Period II (5500 BCE–4800 BCE) and Period III (4800 BCE–3500 BCE)

These two period are also known by the names ceramic Neolithic, as they started using pottery and later Chalcolithic. During these periods, they have started manufacturing technique and utilize the much advanced techniques for Glazed faience beads and terracotta figurines. Figurines of females were decorated with paint and had diverse hairstyles and ornaments. Two flexed burials were found in Period II with a red ochre cover on the body. And in these eras many trade evidence had found as people passionately engaged them to produce the things per people requirements at that time [21].

Medical Technology

In second and third phase of the Mehrgrah, the utmost thing started has of the technique of dental surgery and use of medicinal plants for different diseases. The archeologist believes that it has the foundation of medical sciences and

Figure-6: Evidence of Dental Surgery

these discoveries revealed that the inhabitants of the Civilization have intelligent to think about these and invented solution of their problems (Figure-6). The evidences show that

the people of Mehrgrah were the founder of proto dentistry along with the farming culture [22].

Music and Entertainment Programs

According to archeologist no civilization has been discovered so far and it was not only the oldest civilization, but it made many of us surprised because as per the evidence which was found showed the level of perfection, they people had were so awesome especially their art. Many clay and painting have found which depicted that women are worshipping and men wearing turban on their head (Naqvi and Muhammad, 1990). They have also made the music tools and have group of musicians and entertainment programs (Figure-7). tools and have group of musicians and entertainment programs (Figure-7).

Figure-7: Mehrgrah Band Figurine

Trade, Transportation and Communication

There is confirming for the advancement of exchange frameworks between the majority of the major topographical areas from as ahead of schedule as the seventh thousand years BC at Mehrgrah. The significant frameworks reported amid the early nourishment delivering time. The Proof for exchange is basically relics produced using crude materials with limited sources, for example, marine shell, agate, carnelian, lapis lazuli, turquoise, shaded chert and jaspers, serpentine, steatite and copper. Amid the regionalization period, there was an expansion in the import of crude materials from far off sources. Destinations, for example, Mehrgrah end up focal place settlements, where crude materials (copper, shell, agate, and chert) were prepared for neighborhood and local utilization (particularly starting in Mehrgrah, period iii). These focuses additionally started creating earthenware production for trade to the hinterlands. The early sustenance creating period has an economy considering nourishment generation however deficient with regards to earthenware production. Bigger creatures were utilized also for footing and for transportation [23]. Protest made by potters, metallurgists, dot and adornment produces additionally show status separation. Fine painted products and particular vessels shapes item at Mehrgrah for neighborhood and provincial exchange [24].

Foreign Affairs

The general population of Mehrgrah Human advancement have associated or related with the, Central Asia and Greek Civilization. Adornments of ocean shell, limestone, turquoise, lapis lazuli and sandstone have additionally been found. Ocean shells from the Makran drift and lapis lazuli from Badakshan

demonstrates great contact and exchange encompassing districts. A solitary ground stone hatchet was found in an internment, and a few more were gotten from the surface. These ground stone tomahawks are the soonest to originate from a stratified setting in Greek and central Asia [25].

Stamps, Seals and Currency

Seals are thought to show people or first class bunches who controlled access to and conveyance of fundamental merchandise. The fixing were rolled or stamped on dirt or bitumen to seal holders or packs of merchandise; they most likely had custom significance and in addition filling monetary needs. Different sorts of seals have been found at a considerable lot of the early destinations (Mahrgrah, Rehman Dheri, Damb Sadaat and so forth) and were in the long run explained into the flawless stone seals with content of the coordination time [26].

Food and Agriculture

Mehrgrah (now in Pakistan) with rich green vegetation was suited to be the middle for early human progress in the Indian subcontinent and for the change from chasing and assembling networks to networks with settled horticulture and tamed creatures [27]. Mehrgrah gives an essential confirmation to the change from chasing, social occasion and pastoralism to a subsistence economy, fixated on settled agribusiness and the taming of wild creatures. Horticulture may have enabled individuals to wind up inactive, set up changeless towns and towns and end up mindful of the social arrangement of the social orders. Wheat and grain were developed from the earliest starting point of horticulture and among the natural products, jujube, stones of date palm and grape seeds were first utilized (Figure-8). The spread of agribusiness hence was basically the extension of the exceedingly fruitful example of wheat and grain generation and taming of

Steers, sheep and goat that developed at Mehrgrah region. The training of creatures gave sustenance all the more promptly. The expanding utilization of stoneware took into consideration stockpiling of sustenance, which supported cooking, and the range in the span of the pots empowered their utilization in different ways [28].

The primary utilization of cotton in the historical backdrop of humanity has been found at Mehrgrah. This demonstrates the profound established alliance of Pakistan's geology and economy to cotton since old ages. The nearby cotton which is the presently white gold for Pakistan's economy has establishes in the old past. The random find of the Mehrgrah cotton strands reveals new insight into the early history of this material plant in the Center East. The by and large acknowledged end third starting second thousand years dates for the principal utilization of cotton, in view of finds from Harappan destinations in the Indus Valley, was at that point pushed back to the fourth thousand years by the revelation of strands and impressions from a cotton texture at Duweilah in Jordan [29]. The confirmation from Neolithic Mehrgrah enables us to think about a significantly prior utilization of cotton in

Figure-8: Evidences of Wheat Cultivation from Mehrgrah

The Old World, dating to the sixth thousand years. Despite the fact that we can't make sure that the cotton string used to string copper dots at Mehrgrah got from an officially trained species, it appears to be clear the cotton all things considered was at that point known and misused for its strands at this period (Figure-9). The collection of conformation of early cotton in Pakistani Baluchistan and in the Indus Valley appears to affirm the theory of a South Asian cause, likely in the more noteworthy Indus region, of one of the Old World cottons [31]. It has seen that the agribusiness starts completely from Close East to South Asia having similitude's in the farming and also culture continuum with eastern Mesopotamia [32].

That the taming of creatures started at Mehrgrah; the relics unearthed from Mehrgrah completely substantiate this reality. Mehrgrah gave confirmation to the neighborhood taming of at any rate dairy cattle and sheep in eastern Baluchistan (Pakistan), with wild goats being abused together with some effectively residential ones. Accompanying with measure decrease was expanding portrayal especially of dairy cattle and sheep in the archeological record in respect to such wild taxa as gazelle, blackbuck, nilgai, water bison, and deer, and additionally in respect to goat. Of the household frames, just goat gave confirmation of in any event a few creatures having been tamed from the earliest starting point of occupation at the site [33].

Figure-9: Reflected-light Micrography of the mineralized cotton fibers, [30].

Decline of Mehrgrah Civilization

Generally, very rare people contributed about the great Mehrgrah civilization in Pakistan particularly its decline. However, the evidences show that the people of Baluchistan have still used the same ways of life as like Mehrgrah people. Evidently, the civilization was not decline but improved with passage of time and their society was changed from hunters and agrarians to warriors. As the majority of the Mehrgrah settlements located at the hill tops and slopes so, due to climate change, the area was hit by severe drought and it is observed that the people of the Mehrgrah spread towards east, south, and

west in search of food and water and settled over there. The period 2500 BCE - 2000 BCE there has been a migration towards Harappa and Mohen-Jo-Daro and also to Nausharo which is 6 km south of Mehrgrah in the wake of Indus Valley Civilization [34].

CONCLUSION & RECOMMENDATION

The people of Mehrgrah Civilization have mother and father-based society, where the head of the family or tribe has the authority to decide for the well-being of the people after discussion with all members of the community. The head of the family or tribe may be designated with the name of Sardar stand for the person who led the family or tribe. They have a traditional system of punishment and rewards that they used for any individual after collective decision by the whole community. Generally, the head of family or tribe has used turban for his identity and honor which is still exist in the area. They have dispersed settlements in the form of huts or villages having bricks made houses. The majority of them were nomads and agrarians, however there have very little evidences regarding their political and governance system in the form of artifacts. The lifestyle and culture of Mehrgrah people has very simple and respectful from the earlier ages. They have enthusiastic agriculturists and worth their products. They have women dominant society and always give respect to women have ability to fed and birth more children. Mostly, they have joint family system and nomadic culture. It is also found that they have the ability to make thread from cotton and to use it for sewing of dresses. They have walls and ceilings of their houses for their protection and privacy. This effort of the people of Mehrgrah declared them the first well known industrial and agrarian society of the World history. Due to faster development in technology, the inhabitants of Mehrgrah civilization have started to use pottery, wheels, vases and vessels for their own use and trade with other communities of that era. While the sentiment of a few archeologists that few of the statues found at the site may have been kids, there are numerous who interface these earthenware figures to the religious convictions of Mehrgrah individuals and the age-old idea of the intensity of nature and female gods. They have also the ability to made defense tools like arrows, and swords from copper ores and also had long distance contact with the Mesopotamia, Central Asia and Greek civilization. They are also known for the rainwater logging system and its use for domestic and agriculture purposes like Sailaba and Trai system, the utmost thing started has of the technique of dental surgery and use of medicinal plants for different diseases. The archeologist believes that it has the foundation of medical sciences and these discoveries revealed that the inhabitants of the Civilization have intelligent to think about these and invented solution of their problems. The evidences show that the people of Mehrgrah were the founder of proto dentistry along with the farming culture. One of the reason archeologists and most of the human believes that the people who lived in Mehrgrah were so civilized because they found the way clothes were stitched and they used to wear clothes because archeologist claims that use of cotton originated from Mehrgrah. This is why Pakistan cotton industry is considered one of the potential sectors for the economy of Pakistan.

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